

A Study of Impact of Social Networking Sites on the Academic Performance of Secondary School Students

Awatramani Richa Deepak¹, Dr Fafal Lalji V²

¹Student, Master of Education, Indira Gandhi National Open University, New Delhi India,
richaawatramani5@gmail.com

²Principal, S.D.Shethia College Of Education Mundra, Kutch, India, fafal03@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research study is to examine the influence of social media on the Academic Performance of Students. Fifty Research questions and Four Research hypotheses guided the study. To achieve this, the Descriptive Survey Research design was adopted. The study focused on students of 9th and 10th standard of secondary school in Gandhidham city area and its surrounding Rural and Urban areas of Kutch district. The sample consists of all the 180 students. The simple random sampling technique was used to select a sample of 180 students. A five point Rating Scale Questionnaire type, titled: Social Media and Academic Performance of Students Questionnaire (SMAAPOS) were used to collect data from the participants. The descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentage were used to analyze the demographic data while inferential statistics of Chi-square (χ^2) test was used in testing the research hypotheses. Research findings showed that a great number of students are addicted to social media. To this end, the researcher recommended that social media should be used for educational purposes as well. Social Networking Sites should be expanded and new pages should be created to enhance academic activities and avoid setbacks in the students' academic performance; and Students should be monitored by teachers and parents on how they use these sites This is to create a balance between social media and academic activities of students to avoid setbacks in the academic performance of the students.

Keywords- Social media, Social networking sites, Social networking, Media, Academic, Secondary School Students, Academic performance, Computer, Impact.

INTRODUCTION (BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY)

The world is today celebrating the improvements in communication technology which has broadened the scope of communication through Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs). Modern Technology in communication no doubt has turned the entire world into a "Global village". But as it is, technology like two sides of a coin, bring with it both negative and positive sides. It helps people to be better informed, enlightened, and keeping abreast with world developments. Technology exposes mankind to a better way of doing things. Social networking sites include: Twitter, Yahoo Messenger, Facebook, Messenger, Blackberry Messenger (BBM), Whatsapp, messenger, Skype, Google talk, Google Messenger, Instagram, Snapchat, Google Duo and many more. These networking sites are used by most people to interact with old and new friends, physical or internet friends

The advent of social media has impacted significantly on how students learn and the mode instructors teach. In today higher education settings, social media has influence instructors, students, and others to cooperate with each other on the tasks of knowledge construction in learning and teaching environments.

Social media applications can strengthen class material and positively influence discussions collaborative work, and authoring. Educators and researchers are constantly experimenting with social media technologies hoping to stimulate critical thinking skills, collaboration, and knowledge construction (James). However, the fact that these media are generally open to the world implies a need to carefully consider its' benefits, impacts and risks of openness as well as need for ongoing communication with students in order to address their concerns and deal with issues in the use of social media as they arise.

With these developments in technology social networking sites have become more and more popular among students and a major concern have arose over how the use of social media sites affects their academic performances.

Review of Literature

The internet is an interconnected computer networks that use the standard internet protocol suite to serve billions of users worldwide. It consists of millions of private, public, academic, business and government networks that range from local to global scope that are linked by a broad array of electronic, wireless and optical networking technologies. The advancement of media technology has had a great influence on the way people now communicate on a daily basis. The use of the social media among the youth of today is growing by the day and gaining more and more popularity among students. It is a way to make connections, not only on campus but with friends outside of school. Social networking is a way that helps people feels that they belong to community. Its increased popularity has raised concern over how the time spent and student activities on these sites could impact their performance in school.

Several studies have been carried out by different researchers to assess how the use of social media impact student academic performance. Choney, (2010), MehMood & Taswir, (2013), Kist (2008), Jacobsen & Forste, (2011), believe

that the use of technology such as internet is one of the most important factors that can influence IJSER International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research Volume 9, Issue 3, March-2018 1457 ISSN 2229-5518 IJSER © 2018 <http://www.ijser.org> educational performance of students positively or negatively. It stated that many parents and guardians are worried that students now spend too much time on Facebook and other social media sites and do not have enough time to study.

Hasnain, et al (2015) carried out a research to study the relationship between the use of social media and students' academic performance in Pakistan. The results suggest, social media has an inverse relationship with academic performance. Social media platform used in a positive manner it can help students and youth in gaining knowledge that can be used to enhance their academic performance.

Raut & Patil (2016) highlights how social media influenced education sector the study revealed various positive and negative impacts of social media on education or students. It also highlighted measure to minimize the negative impact of social media on students' academic performances such as; moderating their access to social media sites, reducing the amount of time spent on social network sites.

Olubiyi (2012) noted that these days' students are so engrossed in the social media that they are almost 24 hours online. Even in classrooms and lecture theatres, it has been observed that some students are always busy ping, or Facebook, while lectures are on.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The world today is a global market in which the internet is the most important sort of information. Since the advent of social media sites in the 1990s, it is assumed in some quarters that the academic performance of students is facing a lot of neglect and challenges. There is a deviation, distraction and divided attention between social networking activities and their academic work. It is observed that students devote more attention to social media than they do to their studies. Students' addictiveness to social networks, students' frequency of exposure to social network, social media network that the students are more exposed to and the influence of social media as a medium of interaction between students has been part of discussion in recent times and which have imparted on their academic performance. Instead of students reading their books, they spend their time chatting and making friends via the social media and this might definitely have influence on their academic performance, because when you do not read, there is no way you can perform well academically. It is a common sight to see a student chatting in sensitive and highly organized places like church, mosque and lecture venues. Some are so carried away that even as they are walking along the high way, they keep chatting.

The manufacturing and distribution of equally sophisticated cellular phones has complicated the situation, as students no longer need to visit a cybercafé before they send and receive messages. Attention has been shifted from visible to invisible friends, while important ventures like study and writing might be affected in the process. This phenomenon has become a source of worry to many who believe in knowledge and skill acquisition.

In recent times social media have been a major stay in the minds of students and the world at large thereby causing a lot of drastic measure by students, teacher and even educational administrators at large. It is therefore of great importance to explore some of the trending issues facing students' academic performance as a result of social media. Students at all levels of learning now have divided attention to studies, as a result of available opportunities to be harnessed from social media. Whether these opportunities promote studies is a question that needs to be answered. Thus, the problem this study investigates is the influence of social media networks on the academic performance of secondary school students.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY:

This study is significant to the teachers, parents and students. This study will help the teachers of the school to know the influence that social media has on their students, so as to assist them to enlighten and create awareness to the students on the possible influence it has on them. The study is of significant to parents in the sense that they will know the possible effects these social media usage has on their children, so as to serve as watch-dog to their children on the usage of the social networking site.

The study will enable the students of the senior level so that they will be aware that, apart from the social benefits of this social networking site, using the sites more than necessary will pose possible dangers to their health. It will be relevant in assisting students in understanding the diversity of social media. It will provide relevance material for students and other researchers undertaking similar research. The study will help researchers with more information on the Influence of social media on student's academic performance.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this study generally is to examine the influence of Social Media on the Academic Performance of Secondary School Students Specifically, the study seeks;

- 1) To study the effect of social networking sites on the achievement of secondary school students.
- 2) To study the effect of social networking sites on the achievement of secondary school students with respect to their gender.
- 3) To study the effect of social networking sites on the achievement of secondary school students with respect to their academic performance.
- 4) To study the level of student’s addictiveness to social networking sites affect the academic performance of students.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses are formulated to empirically validate the above objectives:

- There will be no significant difference between mean scores of achievement of secondary school students with respect to their impact of social networking sites.
- There will be no significant difference between mean scores of achievement of secondary school students with respect to their gender on impact of social networking sites.
- There will be no significant difference between opinions of secondary school students on social networking sites with respect to their academic performance.
- There will be no significant difference between opinions of secondary school student’s addictiveness on social networking sites.

RESEARCH METHOD OF THE STUDY

Research methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem. It is a scientific process of defining various steps involved in study. The research design adopted for the study was a descriptive survey. A positive paradigm has been considered. It is best suited for the Quantative research orientation because researchers in this study were interested in quantifying data. This design is considered appropriate because it enables the researcher to generate data through the standardized collection procedures based on highly structured research instrument(s) and well defined study concepts and related variables.

A questionnaire including all the variables involved in the study was prepared. The questionnaire was distributed among 4 schools of rural and urban areas of Gandhidham District.

According to Kothari (2004), research methodology is a method to analytically explain the research problem. It may be described as a science of analysis how research is done systematically.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The population in this research are the students of Secondary level Students. The population of the study will include students of 9th and 10th standard of secondary school in Gandhidham city area and its surrounding Rural areas of Kutch district.

TOTAL NUMBER OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS	TOTAL NUMBER OF 9TH CLASS STANDARD STUDENTS IN 2017-2018 SESSION	TOTAL NUMBER OF 10TH STANDAR D STUDENT S IN 2018-2019 SESSION	TOTAL NUMBER OF STUDENTS IN THE POPULATI ON
18	1800	1800	1800

The sample of the study will consists of 10% of 9th standard of secondary schools in Gandhidham and its surrounding Rural area of Kutch district passed out during academic session 2017-2018 and who will study in 10th standard in the academic session 2018- 2019. Random sampling method will be used to select secondary schools and stratified sampling technique will be used to select students from the school in the 9th standard classes. The sample will be comprised randomly of 180 students from Gandhidham city area and its surrounding Rural area.

RESEARCH TOOL

A well-constructed and self-developed questionnaire titled “Social Media and Academic Performance of Students Questionnaire (SMAAPOS)” was used to get the desired information from the students. The questionnaire was divided into two sections (A and B). Section A was for collection of information on personal data of respondents while Section B consisted of questions that elicited responses from the respondents with response options: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD).

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

The 4 Secondary Schools (i.e. 2 rural and 2 urban schools) are selected by random Sampling. In order to achieve above laid down objectives questionnaire tool is used to collect primary data from the students. Data are collected personally by visiting the selected Schools of the Gandhidham and its nearby rural and urban areas by distributing 180 copies of questionnaires to male students and female students who use SNS.

Achievement of the students will be analyzed using the descriptive statistics with respect to their impact of social networking sites. Impact of social networking sites will be categorized on the level of using hours students. Scores of examination of 9th standard students will be taken as achievement of the students and chi-square test will be used to find out significant difference of student’s group.

Opinions of the students on 5-Point Rating Scale will be analysed and interpreted using non-parametric tests chi-square tests. So in procedure of data analysis descriptive statistics , percentage, chi-square tests ,etc will be calculated with the help of Ms-Excel.

Before collecting data, the purpose of the present study was made clear to the respondents. They were also given instructions and whenever required the researcher had helped them to fill up the tool. The researcher then had ensured that the respondents responded on each item and in cases where the responses were missing , then the concerned respondents were requested again to fill up the missing information.

METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

Data Analysis is the process of systematically applying statistical and/or logical techniques to describe and illustrate, condense and recap, and evaluate data. An essential component of ensuring data integrity is the accurate and appropriate analysis of research findings. According to Sukhia and Mehrotra“ , Analysis of data means studying the tabulated material in order to determine inherent facts of meaning.”(Cited in S.P.Sukhia and others,1965,page:155)

Responses from the questionnaire were analyzed using the descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentage, and inferential statistics of Chi-square. Descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentages were used in analyzing demographic variables and research questions while the inferential statistics of Chi-square was also used to test the stated hypotheses at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance.

MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

A discussion on the major findings of any piece of research study is helpful enough to realize the real gist and essence of the study to its reader.

George Mouly has rightly said that “The findings and the conclusions are the expressions of the investigator’s personal interpretations of the facts he has uncovered.”(Cited in Deepika Bhadrash Shah , 1995 , p:200

An attempt has been made here to elucidate the major finding of the present research study as precisely as possible.

Major findings of the study are as follows:

- ❖ Student’s exposure to social media network has significant influence on students’ academic performance. This corresponds with the findings of Olubiyi (2012) which states that these days’ students are so engrossed in the social media that they are almost 24 hours online. Even in classrooms and lecture theatres, it has been observed that some students are always busy doing ping, or keeping online on facebook, while lectures are on. Times that ought be channelled towards learning, academic research and innovating have been crushed by the passion for meeting new friends online, and most times busy discussing trivial issues. Hence most students’ academics suffer setback as a result of distraction from the social media.
- ❖ Use of social media has significant influence on the academic performance of the students. This goes in line with the observations of Nicole Ellison, (2007) which noted that, the improved usage of Websites has become a worldwide phenomenon for quite some time. What began out as being a hobby for several

computer literate people has converted to a social norm and existence-style for individuals from around the globe.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

In the light of the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Students should be educated on the influence of Social media on their academic performance.
2. Students should be monitored by teachers and parents on how they use these sites.
3. Teachers should ensure they use the social media as a tool to improve the academic performance of students in schools.
4. Students should better manage their study time in and prevent distractions that can be provided by the social media. There should be a decrease in the number of time spent by students while surfing the net.
5. Social Networking Sites should be expanded and new pages should be created to enhance academic activities and avoid setbacks in the students' academic performance.
6. The students should create a balance between chit-chatting and academic activities. More attention should be directed to research.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER STUDIES

The present research study opens avenues for a good number of research studies to be carried out in the future in the same area.

The aspects and the variables which could not be covered in the present study can also be put to test to enlighten those factors which are associated with the attitudes towards teaching and the formation of positive attitudes.

- ✓ This study serves as a basis for further research study on Social media and the academic performance of students.
- ✓ Similar studies should be conducted in other states of the federation so as to bring about improvement in the academic performance of students through the use of Social media networks and to create more pages for research and academic activities, thereby avoiding distraction which leads to deviation from their academic works.
- ✓ Institutions should form a committee to monitor and control the excessive use of SNS.
- ✓ SNS should be used as an e-learning tool.
- ✓ SNS should be used in getting educational materials for student's assignments and project work.
- ✓ SNS should be used as a platform to interact with their friends and faculties.
- ✓ The institution should encourage students to publish articles on SNS to improve their communicational skills and writing skills.

CONCLUSION

The result from the findings of this study showed that, though Social media have negative effects on teenagers such as lack of privacy, distracting students from their academic work, taking most of their productive time, and such like, they also have benefits and can be used appropriately.

For instance, students can form online communities in order to plan for a project, have group discussions about class material, or use the Social networking sites(SNS) as a way to keep in contact when a student who has been absent needs to be updated on current academic information.

The findings of this study and earlier ones showed some noteworthy results. The first independent variable influencing the academic performance of students, that is, social media participation was negatively related with students' outcome, while the other independent variables were positively related with students' outcome.

The results of this study suggest that lecturers should come up with a template on how their students can maximize the benefits of Social media, that school management should incorporate rules and regulations on the use of the social media in the school and, that the government should put in place adequate control measures to regulate their use among students and lecturers.

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